

CONSTANT LIFE DIAGRAMS FOR WOOD COMPOSITES AND POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue performance of wood composites and polymer matrix composites at many R ratios ($\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}$) is conveniently summarised in the form of constant life diagrams. These diagrams are asymmetric as a result of the static compressive strength (σ_{UCS}) being less than the static tensile strength (σ_{UTS}). The position of the maximum in the constant life line envelope is offset to the right of the alternating stress axis and it corresponds to an R ratio closely equal to $\sigma_{\text{UCS}}/\sigma_{\text{UTS}}$ where the likelihood of failure in compression or tension is equal and the stress range also reaches its maximum value. Recommendations are made for a test methodology for evaluating composite systems in fatigue which minimises test time.

Keywords: Fatigue, constant life diagrams, wood composites, polymer matrix composites, R ratio, failure mechanisms, fatigue test methodology.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Aims

The development of wind turbine blade technology in the UK has led to the generation of a large data base of high cycle fatigue data (1) for wood composites based on different species/joint configurations (2). Extensive S-N data has been accumulated and constant life diagrams have been generated from this data and used to predict fatigue life (3) under complex loading (4). Polymer matrix composites are also used extensively for the fabrication of commercial turbine blades and in many other applications where dynamic loads are involved but there are surprisingly few constant life diagrams published in the literature for these materials, unlike metals for which copious information exists (5).

Wood and polymer matrix composites are both orthotropic fibre reinforced materials and unlike metals they are vulnerable to compressive loads. In general static compressive strengths are less than static tensile strengths and compressive failure occurs in a shear/buckling mode. Constant life diagrams for wood composites reveal the striking differences between fatigue behaviour in tension and compression and it is instructive to make comparisons with polymer matrix composites.

The overall aims of this paper are to examine constant life lines for polymer matrix composites, to explain the asymmetrical form of constant life line envelopes in terms of the loading mode and to suggest a test methodology for evaluating composite systems in fatigue for life prediction purposes which requires the minimum amount of test time.

1.2. The form of constant life diagrams

Stress-based constant life diagrams are constructed from S-N data at different R ratios where the R is the ratio of the minimum stress (σ_{\min}) to the maximum stress (σ_{\max}) (6). Figure 1 demonstrates a

Figure 1. Schematic of various R ratios and their relative positions.

range of R ratios in different constant amplitude, cyclic loading modes, namely compression-compression (C-C), compression-tension (C-T), tension-compression (T-C) and tension-tension (T-T). The minimum stress is always taken as the most negative value when calculating the R ratio which together with the stress range is sufficient to define the form of the cyclic stress. Alternatively the alternating stress, σ_{alt} , (half the stress range) and the mean stress, σ_{mean} , define the form of the cyclic

Figure 2. Schematic of the framework of constant life diagrams.

stress. If we construct a framework for a constant life diagram by plotting σ_{mean} versus σ_{alt} , Figure 2, then radial lines represent constant R ratios. Passing from right to left across the diagram the zero alternating stress limit to the constant life diagram will occur at σ_{mean} equal to the ultimate tensile strength, σ_{uts} , at $R=1$. T-T cyclic stresses fall in the range $R=1$ to 0 and at $R=0$, $\sigma_{\text{min}} = 0$. From $R=0$ to -1 (reversed loading) cyclic stresses are T-C and from $R=-1$ to $-\infty$ cyclic stresses are C-T. At the point when σ_{max} falls just below zero stress the loading mode becomes C-C and R flips from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$. The C-C zone ranges from $R=+\infty$ down to 1 at the the zero alternating stress limit in compression where σ_{mean} reaches the ultimate compressive strength, σ_{ucs} .

2. Review of constant life diagrams for orthotropic materials

The low density of wood compared to polymer matrix composites allows thicker specimens to be fatigue tested in compression which eliminates the usual buckling problems which bedevil slender polymer composite test pieces. As a result a considerable amount of S-N data has been accumulated in C-C, C-T and T-C modes and together with T-T data these results have been used to construct constant life diagrams such as Figure 3 for *Khaya ivorensis*, laminated from 4mm thick rotary cut veneer.

Figure 3. Constant life diagram for axially tested *Khaya* for lives of 10^5 , 10^6 and 10^7 cycles to failure including constant R ratio lines from Bonfield and Ansell (1).

Mean stress is plotted versus alternating stress for each constant life and the lines converge on σ_{uts} at the right hand side of the diagram, and on σ_{ucs} at the left hand side of the diagram. The life lines are non-linear, unlike Goodman lines, and the maximum value of σ_{alt} occurs to the right of the σ_{alt} axis. A unique feature of the results for *Khaya* occurs at the boundary between C-C and C-T loading at $R=\pm\infty$. A point of inflexion is noted where the failure mechanism passes from mixed to single mode and at this point the constant life lines converge due to the flatness of S-N curves in compression-compression.

Fibre composite structures are frequently subjected to complex spectrum loads, including cycles with compressive components. The difficulty in measuring compressive data and the enormous range of specimen lay ups and fibre and resin types has resulted in the publication of relatively few constant life lines for polymer matrix composites and life prediction is based on approximate assumptions being made. Where data is available, eg. (7), the constant life lines, Figure 4, share some of the features common to wood composites. σ_{uts} for the carbon, Kevlar and hybrid polymer composites is

Figure 4. Constant life, or Goodman, diagram showing the effect of mean stress on the fatigue response of unidirectional CFRP/KFRP hybrids from Adam et al (7).

considerably greater than σ_{UCS} and the constant life lines are offset to the right hand side of the alternating stress axis ($R=-1$) so that the maxima do not occur at $R=-1$. The composites have not been tested in the C-C and C-T zones close to $R=\pm\infty$ where a point of inflexion might conceivably occur as a result of compressive buckling.

Harris et al (8) present constant life diagrams for unidirectional and $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ CFRP at R ratios of -0.6, -0.3 and 0.1, Figure 5. The constant life envelopes are offset to the right and data points for lives of 10^5 and 10^6 cycles are joined by straight lines. In Figure 6 parabolic curves are fitted to the data points in Figure 5 substituting the parameters m and a for the mean stress and alternating stress respectively, where $a = \sigma_{alt}/\sigma_t$ and $m = \sigma_{mean}/\sigma_t$ and where σ_t is the tensile strength. The equation used is of the form, $a = f(1-m)(c+m)$,

Figure 5. Goodman diagram for (Δ, Δ) XAS/914 unidirectional and (\square, \square) T800/6376 $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ composites. ----, 10^5 cycles; ----, 10^6 cycles. After Harris et al (8).

Figure 6. Normalized Goodman diagram for (Δ, Δ) XAS/914 unidirectional and (\square, \square) T800/6376 $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ composites. The disposition of points relating to lives of 10^5 and 10^6 cycles may be judged by reference to Figure 6. After Harris et al (8).

where $c = \sigma_c/\sigma_t$ and f is a curve fitting constant. It is not clear whether the parabola fit the data points convincingly nor whether the curve fitting constant used has any relationship to damage accumulation in tension or compression. Inspection of Figure 5 suggests that the maximum in the constant life diagram should fall at an R ratio somewhere between $R=-0.6$ and $R=0.1$. The curve fitting analysis is developed further by Adam et al (9) using the equation,

$$a = 2[(1-m)(c+m)]^x,$$

Figure 7. Normalized constant life diagram for $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ T800/5245 laminate. The experimental data for 10^4 and 10^5 cycles are fitted to the function $a = 2[(1-m)(c+m)]^x$. After Adam et al (9).

Figure 8. Constant life diagram for T800/5245 CFRP from Adam et al (10).

where x is a numerical exponent which depends on the median fatigue life. In Figure 7 m is plotted against a and fitted to constant life points for a $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ T800/5245 CFRP laminate. Inspection of Figure 7 suggests that the maximum in the constant life diagram should fall at an R ratio somewhere between $R=-1$ and $R=-0.3$. More data has been added to to Figure 7 in a recent publication (10) and this is presented in Figure 8 for constant lives of 10^4 , 10^5 , 10^6 and 10^7 cycles. The authors of this paper have sketched in the 10^4 cycles constant life line which suggests a pronounced asymmetry to the line envelope and a maximum close to $R=-0.6$.

Figure 9. Constant life diagram of the G/CFRP coupon specimens from Bach (11).

Other constant life data for composites in the literature tends to be limited, for example Bach's (11) results for G/CFRP hybrids, Figure 9. This diagram derived from σ_{UTS} and $R=-1$ and $R=0.1$ S-N curves suggests that a constant life line maximum will occur between these two R ratios.

3. Discussion

3.1. Predicting the maximum in the constant life line.

The form of constant life diagrams for wood composites and polymer matrix composites is similar and appears to bear some relationship to the values of σ_{UTS} and σ_{UCS} . At an R ratio equal to the ratio of the σ_{UCS} to the σ_{UTS} there should be an equal likelihood of fatigue failure in compression or tension. At this R ratio σ_{alt} and hence the stress range reaches its maximum value and each constant life line should reach its maximum value. For example in Figure 8 $\sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$ is equal to -0.55 and if the stress range is plotted versus R ratio, Figure 10, it is clear that this $\sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$ ratio corresponds to the

Figure 10. Stress range versus R ratio depicting maximum at $R = \sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$.

maximum in the constant life diagram. The wood composites data of Figure 3 shows a correspondence between the $\sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$ R ratio, equal to -0.61, and the maximum in the constant life diagram. The KFRP results from Figure 4 also confirm this trend with a $\sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$ R ratio equal to about -0.2 reflecting the poor performance of Kevlar in compression.

3.2. Determining the form of constant life diagrams with limited data

Constant life diagrams such as those presented in Figures 3 and 8 allow the form of S-N curves at other R ratios to be interpolated with reasonable accuracy. However it is necessary to measure σ_{UCS} and σ_{UTS} and to produce S-N curves at several R ratios. A simplifying approach is to triangulate constant life diagrams from σ_{UCS} and σ_{UTS} and S-N data at $R=-1$. The triangulated diagram fits within the envelope of the full life line envelope, Figure 3, and new composite systems can be evaluated

Figure 11. Simplified constant life diagram of scarf jointed poplar, laminated wood composite.

quickly, eg. scarf-jointed poplar composite, Figure 11. A further improvement in producing accurate life line envelopes based on limited fatigue data would involve testing at $R=-1$ and at $R=\sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$ (or perhaps at $R=\sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$ alone) as the maximum for each constant life line would be identified. Lines could then be drawn between the σ_{UCS} , σ_{UTS} and the $R=-1$ and $R=\sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$ coordinates to determine a reasonably accurate approximate envelope.

Life prediction, based on relating fatigue life to a complex spectrum, can be achieved by calculating the approximate form of S-N curves at any R ratio by interpolating the simplified constant life diagram envelope, rainflow counting the complex spectrum and applying Miner's Rule.

4. Conclusions

- Constant life diagrams for wood composites and polymer matrix composites are asymmetric as a result of the static compressive strength (σ_{UCS}) being less than the static tensile strength (σ_{UTS}).
- The position of the maximum in the constant life line envelope is offset to the right of the alternating stress axis and it corresponds to an R ratio closely equal to $\sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$ where the likelihood of failure in compression or tension is equal and the stress range also reaches its maximum value.
- New composite systems can be rapidly evaluated in fatigue by measuring σ_{UCS} and σ_{UTS} and S-N data at $R=-1$ and $R=\sigma_{UCS}/\sigma_{UTS}$ to allow the construction of an approximate set of constant life lines.
- Such constant life lines can be interpolated and the resulting S-N curves can be applied to complex spectrum loads to enable life prediction to be carried out.

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